

Poly(lactic acid)/halloysite nanocomposites films by solvent casting method

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Abstract

Poly (lactic) acid (PLA)/natural halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) films were prepared by solution casting method to investigate their properties for packaging applications. Tensile test results revealed that the maximum tensile elastic modulus (1.403 ± 0.05 GPa) and tensile strength (52.75 ± 1.8 MPa) were achieved with addition of 5 (w/w %) of HNTs. Electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces, implied that the reinforcing mechanism were subjected to the interfacial interaction between HNTs and PLA. Infrared spectra revealed that the end hydroxyl groups of PLA chemically interacted with HNTs' outer surface siloxane groups via hydrogen bonding. In addition, the contact angle test and thermogravimetric analysis were used to investigate the surface wettability and thermal stability of the PLA/HNT films.

1 Introduction

To this day, petrochemical-based plastics occupy a predominate place in many industries, but the emission of CO₂ and green-house gases during the processing of these plastics have led to global warming. Also, the non-biodegradability of these plastics creates issues in terms of waste disposal. Hence, environmental concerns over plastic materials have raised interest in the use of biodegradable alternatives in many industries.

Poly (lactic acid) (PLA) is an environmental friendly alternative for petrochemical-based plastics and it is extracted from a fermentation process of natural sugar feedstock such as corn and sugar beet [1, 2]. PLA is a suitable candidate for packaging because of its hydrophobicity and biodegradability [3].

However, its low mechanical properties, thermal stability, and gas barrier properties restrict its use in a wide range of potential packaging applications [1, 3-6]. Therefore, in recent years, much attention has been paid to enhance the characteristics of PLA by adding different type of nano-fillers such as organo-modified montmorillonite (o-MMT) [3-5], microcrystalline cellulose (MMC) [7], silica particles [8], multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) [8], biphasic calcium phosphate (BSP) [6], and sepiolite [3]. To the author's knowledge, there appears to be no studies conducted with the aim of reinforcing PLA using natural halloysites (HNTs) using solvent casting.

Halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) are natural aluminosilicate ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_{4-n}\text{H}_2\text{O}$) crystallites with nano-tubular structures [9]. Typically, the length of HNTs varies from 50-5000 nm, with an external diameter of 20-200 nm and internal diameter of 10-70nm [10, 11]. HNTs possess several remarkable properties such as biodegradability, low surface hydroxyl groups and unique crystalline structure. Recently HNTs have been used as nanofillers to reinforce various polymers [12].

There are very few studies on PLA/HNT composites. Very recently, natural HNT-incorporated PLA nanocomposites were prepared by melt extrusion using a master-batch dilution process and reported improvements in mechanical properties [13]. They reported that the Young's modulus and tensile strength increased by 14% and 15%, respectively with addition of 6 (w/w %) HNTs. Another study reported the improvements in mechanical properties of PLA composites prepared by incorporating quaternary ammonium salt-treated HNTs [14].

In this study, halloysite nanotubes were used to prepare PLA/HNT films by using solution casting method by adding 2.5, 5, 7.5 and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs. The properties of nanocomposite such as mechanical, thermal, chemical interaction and morphology were studied through tensile test, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Poly lactide acid (PLA) (grade 3051D, $M_n = 93,500$ g/mol, $T_g = 65.5$ °C (NatureWorks USA)), halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) (Imerys Tableware New Zealand Clay Ltd.) and chloroform (Sigma Aldrich Pvt. Ltd.) were used as matrix, filler and solvent, respectively.

2.2 Preparation of PLA/HNT films

5 % w/v of PLA solution was prepared by dissolving 5g of PLA pellets in 100 ml pure chloroform. Then, solution was stirred vigorously for about 5 hours on magnetic stirrer at 700 rpm. Next, appropriate amounts of amount weights of HNTs (of 0, 2.5, 5, 7.5 and 10 %) with respected to weight of PLA were swelled into chloroform and sonicated for ½ hour. Afterwards, HNTs were mixed with PLA solution and stirred overnight at 700rpm. Approximately 30g from the resultant solution was poured into glass petri dishes (diameter of 20 cm) and spread evenly. The dishes were allowed to dry for about 24h at room temperature. Afterward, the dishes were further dried at 40 °C in vacuum oven for 8h to remove the remaining solvent and prevent the solvent from acting as plasticizers. Finally the films were peeled off from the petri dishes after being immersed in distilled water for 10 min.

2.3 Tensile Testing

Young's modulus (E), tensile strength (σ), and strain at the point of rupture (ϵ) of PLA/HNT films were measured with TA XT Plus Texture Analyzer (Stable Micro System, UK) based on the ASTM D 882-02 standard. Strips of films (10.0 x 2.0 cm) were clamped between the manual grips (without sharp edges) and a 5kg load cell was used. Films

were tested at a cross section speed of 0.7 mm/s and the initial grip to grip distance was set at 50 mm.

2.3 Morphological tests

The morphology of fractured surfaces of tensile samples with 5 and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs were investigated using a field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) model Hitachi SU8010.

2.4 Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR analysis was conducted to identify the chemical interactions occurring inside the PLA/HNT films and the chemical composition uniformity of the samples. All samples were examined using the *Thermo Scientific IS10* with a wavelength range of 500-4000 cm^{-1} with 0.4 cm^{-1} resolution and 32 scans.

2.5 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

TGA was carried out using *TGA Q50* to investigate the thermal stability of the PLA/HNT films, from a temperature range of 25 °C to 800 °C at a rate of 10 °C /min under nitrogen atmosphere.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical Properties

The typical stress-strain curves of PLA/HNT films are shown in Fig. 1 and showed brittle fracture of the composite films. Young's modulus (E), tensile strength (TS) and elongation at break (ϵ) which obtained from tensile test are summarized in Table 1. Mechanical properties such as E and TS of PLA films have increased with the addition of HNTs. This could be due to the good interaction between the HNTs and PLA at low HNT concentration. Both E and TS have increased with the addition of 2.5 and 5 (w/w %) of HNTs. However E and TS gradually decreased at higher HNT concentrations, 7.5 and 10 (w/w %).

Fig. 1: Typical stress-strain graph of PLA/HNT films

Table 1: Tensile test results of PLA/HNT films

HNT concentration (wt%)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
0	0.859±0.06	36.66±2.57	6.15±0.15
2.5	1.264±0.06	45.50±1.99	4.93±0.17
5	1.403±0.05	52.75±1.79	4.79±0.24
7.5	1.374±0.07	47.91±1.85	4.37±0.26
10	1.252±0.12	42.75±2.99	4.76±0.37

In general, E behaves according to the *mixture of law*, which has been explained by a linear equation. But the results of this experiment (trend) shows that the E of the films does not follow a linear relationship with the addition of HNTs, and it was clarified using linear regression analysis. At high HNT concentrations, there is a high probability for HNTs to interact with each other and become aggregated. These aggregations form clusters inside the matrix which lead to high stress concentration areas within nanocomposite. Hence, the material failed easily, it can be concluded that the PLA films with 7.5 (w/w %) and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs may have more clusters of HNTs than the film with 5 (w/w %). At 5 (w/w %), the composites have the optimum E (1.403 ± 0.05 GPa) which is an improvement of 57.75 % when compared with the

pure PLA film. This percent increment of E is higher than the reported E values of solvent casted PLA composites with different types of fillers such as different types of modified montmorillonite [1, 15] and bentonite [7] at their optimum concentrations.

It can be seen that ϵ has decreased with the addition of HNTs with respect to pure PLA films. Furthermore, it can be noted that ϵ decreases with the addition of low concentrations of HNTs and remains constant even at higher concentrations of HNTs. The reason for ϵ to decrease is the reinforcement effect provided by HNTs as a nano-filler, which leads to a structural rigidity of polymer chains. It is worth mentioning here that the behavior of the stress-strain curves of PLA/HNT composites is highly dependable on the 'post-drying' process followed in the preparation of PLA composites [1].

3.2 Morphology

Fig. 2(a, b) shows a SEM micrograph of PLA films with 5 (w/w %) of HNTs. According to the micrograph, the dispersion of HNTs within the matrix is fairly good. However, there appears to be some signs of agglomeration of HNTs as well. The amount of "micro-voids" (as marked by arrows), which occurred due to pulled-out nanotubes during the tensile testing, is very minimal, with 5 (w/w %) HNT concentration. This implies that the interaction between HNTs and PLA is quite strong at this HNT concentration.

In Fig. 2(c), it is possible to note a significant increase in the number of micro-voids (as marked by arrows) as compared to that in Fig. 2(b). This increase implies that the filler-matrix interaction is not that good at high filler loadings (10 (w/w %) HNT). Furthermore, a drastic increase in the degree of agglomeration of HNTs can also be seen (as illustrated in the magnified part of Fig. 2(c)). Fig. 2(c) also shows a noticeable amount of pores which could have been formed due to the removal of matrix (PLA polymer) parts during the tensile testing. These facts indicate that the filler-matrix interaction is not that good at higher HNT concentrations (10 (w/w %) HNT) compared to moderate HNT concentration (5 (w/w %) HNT), thereby proving the trends of mechanical properties of PLA/HNT composites. According to the tensile

test results, mechanical properties such as E and TS of 10 (w/w %) films were less than 5 (w/w %) HNTs films, and were also slightly inferior to the films with 2.5 (w/w %) of HNTs. Weaker mechanical properties could have been the result of (i) poor matrix-filler interaction and (ii) the presence of high degree of HNT aggregation, even though a higher number of HNTs would have provided more opportunities for stress transformation.

3.2 Chemical properties

FTIR results revealed that some HNT functional groups contributed to all the composite films (full range spectra is not presented). O-H stretching of inner-surface hydroxyl groups (3695 cm^{-1}), O-H stretching of inner hydroxyl group (3621 cm^{-1}), and O-H deformation of inner hydroxyl groups (911 cm^{-1}) were present in all the composite films. In addition, the Si-O (in-plane stretching) functional group (1006 cm^{-1}) of HNT appears as a shoulder to the vibration band 1043 cm^{-1} of PLA for all the composite films [16]. Peaks of few functional groups of HNT such as perpendicular Si-O stretching at 1118 cm^{-1} and 750 cm^{-1} and symmetric stretching of Si-O at 799 cm^{-1} are not visible on the full range spectra of composite films, since the intensity of those peaks are relatively low compared to the other main peaks in composite films.

A comparison of the results obtained from pure PLA pallets with those from the composite films revealed that the PLA functional groups contributed to the vibrational modes in all the composite films. C-H stretching vibration of CH_3 groups ($2996, 2946\text{ cm}^{-1}$), stretching vibration of carbonyl group (1747 cm^{-1}), C-H deformation (1452 cm^{-1}), C-O-H groups ($1382, 1360\text{ cm}^{-1}$), -C-O bond stretching (1182 cm^{-1}) in -CH-O- groups of PLA and C-O stretching ($1200\text{-}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were detected in all the composite films [17, 18].

Fig. 2: SEM of PLA composites with (a, b) 5 (w/w %) and (c) 10 (w/w %) of HNTs

As illustrated in Fig. 3, spectra within the range of 3800-3400 cm^{-1} show the presence of O-H groups of pure PLA films and composite films which are contributed by both filler and matrix. The peak at 3648 cm^{-1} of PLA film refers to the hydroxyl groups at the end of the PLA polymer chains [19]. This peak has appeared in the composite films too, but those have been shifted to the higher wave numbers (redshift); the peak has been shifted to 3659 cm^{-1} and 3652 cm^{-1} for the composite films with 5 (w/w %) and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs, respectively. This phenomenon indicates a possibility of hydrogen-bonding of PLA's end hydroxyl groups with the functional group of HNTs. It is also possible to note that the composites with 5 (w/w %) of HNTs have shifted more than the 10 (w/w %) which could have been the result of the composites with 5 (w/w %) HNTs having a higher degree of bonding than the 10 (w/w %) HNT loaded films.

Fig. 3: FTIR spectra within the range of 3800-3400 cm^{-1} .

The elaborated in Fig. 4, spectra within the range 1115-885 cm^{-1} show the FTIR spectra of pure HNT, and composite films with 0, 5 and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs on a common Y-axis plot to compare the wave intensities (absorbance). In general, when considering the FTIR spectra of composites, the intensity of the peaks of the matrix would not change drastically. Even if it changed, there would only be a slight decrease in matrix peak intensity, because the weight percentage of the matrix decreases when adding fillers. However, it would not increase unless there is an overlap with another peak (possibly from the filler). In this case, the intensity of the peak at 1043 cm^{-1} of PLA has

increased with the addition of HNTs. Initial absorbance value of the peak 1043 cm^{-1} of PLA film is 0.11 and it has increased to 0.125 and 0.155 with the addition of 5 (w/w %) and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs, respectively. This could be due to the overlapping of 1043 cm^{-1} with HNTs shifted (red shifted) peak at 1031 cm^{-1} (in plane Si-O stretching). So this shifting implies that the external surface Si-O groups could form a hydrogen-bonding with PLA.

Fig. 4: common Y-axis (absorbance) plot of FTIR spectra within the range of 3800-3400 cm^{-1} .

Considering the peak shifting occurring in both PLA and HNTs, it can be postulated that the end hydroxyl groups of PLA may undergo a hydrogen bonding with HNT's external surface siloxane functional groups (Fig. 5). This chemical interaction is the main reason for the significant improvements in mechanical properties.

Fig. 5: Schematic of possible interaction mechanism between PLA and HNTs.

3.2 Thermal properties

TGA curves of PLA/HNT films are presented in Fig. 6 and results are summarised in Table 1. In the curves of films, there are two major losses (drops in the curves). The first mass loss at around 104 °C could be attributed to the removal of absorbed moisture of the films, while the second mass loss could be due to the chemical de-bonding or degradation of PLA polymer. There is no appreciable trend in the degradation temperature with respect to HNT concentrations at 50% weight loss. In particular, the degradation temperatures fluctuate between 355 °C and 368 °C. In general, it can be seen that the temperature at 50% weight loss does not significantly change with low HNT concentrations (2.5 w/w %), but it drastically increases with the addition of moderate (5 and 7.5 (w/w %)) and high (10 (w/w %)) concentrations of HNTs. Furthermore, the remaining weight percentage at maximum temperature has significantly increased with the addition of HNTs. Thus, it can be stated that the thermal stability of PLA films increases with the addition of HNTs.

The thermal stability increases due to a few reasons, out of which the most dominant factors would be the lumen of HNTs and char residue formation. The length of this particular type of HNTs used in the experiment varies from 100-3000 nm and the lumen diameter varies from 15-70 nm [11, 20]. The thermal stability of HNTs are very high and only at 475-575 °C nanotubes' structural properties start to degrade (HNTs' structural AlOH groups begins to dehydroxylate) [16]. Therefore, the initial stages of degradation would be regulated by the entrapment of degraded products of PLA polymer inside the lumens of HNTs. As a result, it may have led to effective delay in mass transport, thereby increasing thermal stability significantly at high concentrations (especially by adding 7.5 and 10 (w/w %) HNTs into the PLA). As the applied temperature increases, char residue forms within the PLA matrix. However, the degraded products that had diffused into the HNT lumen during early stages could also form new (intermediate) compounds. So these could act as barriers to hinder the diffusion of volatile losses and therefore, thermal stability increases with the addition of HNTs.

Table 2: Summary of the results of TGA of PLA/HNT films

HNT concentration (w/w %)	Temperature at 50% weight loss (°C)	Remaining weight (%) at maximum temperature
0	355	0.2
2.5	353	3.8
5	368	4.9
7.5	374	7.5
10	368	14.8
Pure HNT	-	85

Fig. 6: TGA curves of PLA/HNT films

4.0 Conclusion

PLA/HNT films were successfully prepared by solution casting method by adding 2.5, 5, 7.5 and 10 (w/w %) of HNTs. Tensile test data revealed that the films reinforced with 5 (w/w %) of HNTs yielded the optimum results; tensile elastic modulus and tensile strength significantly improved by 58% and 43%, respectively, due to the better interfacial adhesion between HNTs and PLA. At high HNT loadings, the mechanical properties were slightly inferior than PLA composite films with 5 (w/w %) of HNTs due to the high degree of aggregation of HNTs. SEM micrographs showed more micro-voids and pores in PLA composites with 10 (w/w %) of HNTs compared to 5 (w/w %), which confirmed the low filler-matrix interaction at high HNT loadings. According to FTIR analysis, end hydroxyl groups of

PLA interacted with outer surface siloxane groups of HNTs via hydrogen bonding. TGA results revealed that the thermal stability increased significantly with addition of HNTs due to the char residue and lumens of HNTs. These novel PLA/HNT films may be used as an alternative for petrochemical-based plastic packaging material for food products and this study may broaden the applications of PLA as a biopolymer nanocomposite in near future.

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